

EXPLORING THE EVOLVING LEADERSHIP STYLES UTILIZED IN PRIVATE UNIVERSITIES: A SCHOLARLY ANALYSIS

Dr. Michael Martinson Boakye

Senior Lecturer, J. S. Addo School of Business, Marshalls University College, Ghana

Cite This Article: Dr. Michael Martinson Boakye, "Exploring the Evolving Leadership Styles Utilized in Private Universities: A Scholarly Analysis", *International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research in Arts and Humanities, International Peer Reviewed - Refereed Research Journal*, Volume 9, Issue 1, January - June, Page Number 12-16, 2024.

Copy Right: © DV Publication, 2024 (All Rights Reserved). This is an Open Access Article distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium provided the original work is properly cited.

Abstract:

Leadership style enormously affects the effectiveness of Private Universities or Institutions of Higher Education. This contemporary study describes the state of leadership style of private universities. This paper analysed data collected from 130 respondents comprising students, alumni, faculty and administrative staff of private institution of higher education. Analysis was done in descriptive framework using a descriptive statistics as techniques of analysis. The findings revealed that Transformational leadership style was dominant (mean=3.515) in private universities followed by Authoritarian style (mean=3.132) and Transactional leadership style (mean=3.0538). The study recommended that private university administrators should focus more on transformational leadership since it has more potential to promote institutional effectiveness. This therefore calls for constant training and capacity on how to leverage on the evolving benefit of transformational, transactional and authoritative leadership styles.

Key Words: Leadership Styles, Transformational Leadership, Transactional Leadership, Authoritative Leadership, Private Universities

Introduction:

Leadership play a very important role in the administration of higher education or private university education especially in the process of enhancing promoting the image and the reputation of private universities. Leadership is fundamental to the success and growth of institutions. In private institutions of higher education, effective leadership is very important as these institutions face predictable challenges as compared to their government institutions. This paper aims to describe the evolving leadership styles used in private institutions of higher education, focusing on how these styles influence institutional success. Leadership styles refer to the behavior that individuals or leaders use in an attempt to guide, inspire, and influence others towards achieving common goals. These styles include but are not limited to transformational leadership, transactional, authoritative leadership, laissez faire leadership among others. The objective was to describe leadership styles used in Private Institutions of Higher Education in order to establish which style or styles are predominantly used and its impact on institutional effectiveness.

Review of Literature:

Leadership styles are viewed as a combination of different characteristics and behaviours that are used by leaders for interacting with their subordinates (Mitonga-Monga & Coetzee, 2012). Harris et al (2007) also postulate that leadership style can be defined as the kind of relationship that is used by an individual so as to make people work together for a common goal or objective. Modern leadership styles can be categorized as follows: (1) transformational leadership style, (2) transactional leadership style, (3) culture based leadership, (4) charismatic leadership, and (5) visionary leadership (Harris, et al., 2007). Leadership, psychologist and management gurus' over-time have identified several leadership behaviours /styles of which some have evolved and others too standing the test of time. The numerous leadership theories; Great man theory to trait theory through to modern theories of leadership have yielded great number of leadership styles commonly used by leaders to achieve organisational effectiveness or achieve a goal. They include task oriented, relationship oriented, supportive, delegative, directive and participative styles of leadership.

Authoritarian Leadership Behaviour / Style:

The leader provides constant and direct instructions. Smith (2019) postulates that authoritarian leaders exercise close control over followers and motivate them through strict adherence of rules, regulations and penalties. The leader's directive is final and there is no room for suggestion from followers. Without the participation of the follower, the leader makes all decisions and delegate tasks effectively. The focus of this leadership is on task and results and therefore employee feelings are not considered. The mandate of the leader is to check and reprimand followers in case of disappointing results. Farh and Cheng (2000) sees authoritarian leader as a leader behaviour of asserting strong authority and control over subordinates and demanding unique obedience from them because they have the last say in their organisations and provides a singular mission upon which followers must focus on their job responsibility without uncertainty. Janse (2018) indicates that authoritarian leaders may use coercive power in their leadership process. Janse (20018) identifies the following

weaknesses of authoritarian leader; stifles creativity because leaders direct and execute decisions alone as well as fear of sanctions motivate negatively.

Max Weber Transactional Leadership Behaviour / Style:

Transactional leadership as first identified by Max Weber in 1947 is related to legal relationship or bureaucratic leadership. It is popularly acknowledged as a management leadership style. This is task-oriented and directive style with focus on role of supervision in an organisation and follower performance. Transactional leaders value order and structure in an organisation making good use of intrinsic rewards and punishment as motivating factors for follower's performance. This leader prefers to work with self-motivated followers in a more structured and directed environment. Kendra (2020) expresses that transactional leader's behaviour helps people to perform their best when there is clear and definite chain of command. Rewards and punishment motivates workers, obeying instructions and commands are the basic goal of followers because subordinates need to be carefully monitored to ensure that expectations are met.

Bass Transformational Leadership Behaviour / Style:

Sociologist Max Weber (1947) in his theory advocated transformational leadership which causes changes in individuals and social systems. He uses the word charismatic as a quality of a transformational leader. Charismatic leadership theory focuses on follower perception that a leader is endowed with exceptional qualities. Every transformational leader demonstrates charismatic characteristics such as visionary, personal risk taking, sensitivity to follower needs etc. Bryman (1992) expresses those transformational and charismatic leaders are new leadership because they break links with existing leadership behaviours. Several studies link charismatic to transformational leadership (Bass, 1985)

Bass (1985) in his transformational theory established that leaders can use their perceptions, values, aspirations and expectations to transform the life of the followers to respond positively to organisational needs. Transformational leaders with their qualities cause change in followers and social systems in a way that followers can one day become leaders. Transformational leadership is called relational leadership. Bass (1990) identifies three ways transformational leaders use to influence followers. It involves awareness of followers on task and value, getting followers to concentrate on organisation goals and activating follower needs. On the other hand, Bass & Riggio (2006) highlights that transformational leadership is based on idealized influence, intellectual stimulation, inspiration and motivation, and individual consideration. This style of leading followers inspires positive changes with a lot of energy, passion and zeal from the leader. Whitehead (2018) indicates that transformational leadership through inspiration motivates trusted workforce to take authority over decision making in task performance.

Research Methodology:

The study used both primary and secondary data. The primary data were gathered through questionnaire administration in order to describe leadership style in private university or institutions of higher education. Questions on leadership styles were responded to in order to determine the degree of respondent perception. Data were processed using SmartLPS3 software. The research design for the study was survey using quantitative technique. Total population of 130 respondents was involved in the study covering the junior staff members (25), alumni (5) and continuing students (100) of a private university in the Accra Metropolis using Stratified random sampling to select respondents.

Empirical Results:

Participants responded to questions on leadership styles to measure their opinions and perceptions. The leadership styles describe the state of leadership in an organisation because it impacts followers and organisation as a whole. Laissez faire, transformational, transactional, authoritative, coaching and bureaucratic styles of leadership were the options offered to respondents.

Oxford and Burry Stock (1995) Mean classification criterion was used to interpret the degree of perception or expectation of respondents. They interpret Mean scores as follows: 1.0 – 2.4 = Low Score, 2.5-3.4 = Moderate Score, 3.5-5.0 = High Score.

Descriptive Statistics of State of Leadership Style in Private Universities:

Leadership Style	Mean (SD)	Interpretation
Transformational	3.5154(.37961)	High
Idealized Influence (IIB)	3.7173(.66792)	High
Talks about his/her most important values and beliefs.	3.45(1.065)	
Specifies the importance of having a strong sense of purpose.	3.75(0.883)	
Considers the moral and ethical consequences of decision.	3.85(0.864)	
Emphasizes the importance of having a collective sense of mission.	3.82(0.947)	
Idealized Influence (IIA)	3.7173(.72630)	High
Instils pride in others for being associated with him/her.	3.92(1.024)	
Goes beyond self-interest for the good of the group.	3.83(1.072)	
Acts in ways that builds my respect.	3.82(0.947)	
Displays a sense of power and confidences of decisions.	3.30(1.166)	

Inspirational Motivation	3.1654(.62145)	Moderate
Talks optimistically about the future.	3.25(1.190)	
Talks enthusiastically about what needs to be accounted.	2.73(1.368)	
Articulates a compelling vision of the future.	3.39(1.096)	
Expresses confidence that goals will be achieved.	3.28(1.051)	
Intellectual Simulation	3.1846(.60003)	Moderate
Re-examines critical assumptions to question whether they are appropriate.	3.24(1.062)	
Seeks differing perspectives when solving problems	3.32(1.058)	
Gets me to look at problems from many different	3.11(1.013)	
Suggests new ways of looking at how to complete assignments	3.07(0.908)	
IC	3.7923(.60211)	High
Spends time teaching and coaching.	3.69(0.805)	
Treats me as an individual rather than just as a member of a group.	4.08(0.937)	
Considers me as having different needs, abilities, and aspirations from others.	3.84(0.861)	
Helps me to develop my strengths.	3.56(0.872)	
Transactional	3.0538(.32447)	Moderate
Contingent Reward	3.7442(.57184)	High
Provides me with assistance in exchange for my efforts.	3.22(0.932)	
Discusses in specific terms who is responsible for achieving performance targets.	3.71(0.741)	
Makes clear what one can expect to receive when performance goals are achieved.	4.17(0.949)	
Expresses satisfaction when I meet expectations.	3.88(0.764)	
Management by exception	2.8769(.43607)	Moderate
Fails to interfere until problems become serious.	2.86(.860)	
Waits for things to go wrong before taking action	3.92(.466)	
Shows that he/she is a firm believer in "If it isn't broke don't fix it."	1.19(0.683)	
Demonstrates that problems must become chronic before I take action.	2.19(0.738)	
MEP	2.5404(.42773)	Moderate
Focuses attention on irregularities, mistakes, exceptions and deviations from standards.	3.65(.870)	
Concentrates his/her full attention on dealing with mistakes, complaints, and failures.	3.62(.865)	
Keeps track of all mistakes.	1.67(.534)	
Directs my attention to failures to meet standards.	2.57(.980)	
Authoritative Leadership	3.1321(.90569)	Moderate
My management believes employees need to be supervised closely they are not likely to do their work.	2.90(0.971)	
As a rule, my management believes that employees must be given rewards or punishments in order to motivate them to achieve organisational objectives.	3.25(0.997)	
I feel insecure about my work and need direction	3.41(1.434)	
My management is the chief judge of the achievements of employees.	3.54(1.399)	
My management gives orders and clarifies procedures	2.63(1.370)	
My management believes that most employees in the general population are lazy	3.07(1.182)	
Laissez Faire Leadership	3.1231(.87322)	Moderate
In complex situations my supervisor allows me to work my problems out on my own way	3.31(1.180)	
My management stays out of the way as I do my work	3.40(1.205)	
As a rule, my management allows me to appraise my own work.	3.26(1.172)	
My management gives me complete freedom to solve problems on my own	3.22(1.294)	
In most situations, I prefer little input from my management.	2.48(1.051)	
In general my management feels it is best to leave subordinates alone	3.07(1.215)	
Valid N (listwise) = 130		

Source: Author's Construct, 2022

The Overall Leadership Style	Mean	Std. Deviation
Valid N (list wise) = 130	3.2837	.33155

Scale (Mean): 1-2.4=Low, 2.5-3.4=Moderate, 3.5-5.0 = High (Oxford & Stock, 1995)

Source: Author's Construct, 2023

From the Table, transformational leadership had a High Mean score of 3.515 whereas transactional leadership had Moderate Mean score of 3.053. Authoritative and Laissez faire leadership styles had a Moderate Mean score of 3.132 and 3.123 respectively. The overall leadership style had a Moderate Mean score of 3.283. This indicates the transformational leadership was most prominent style used in the university. This finding supports the assertion of Wang et al (2011) and Sofi and Devanadhen (2015) that transformational leadership style is most used in institutions because it inspire and motivate followers for organisational effectiveness.

Respondents Perception on the Effectiveness of Leadership Styles:

In relation to respondent's agreement to the effectiveness of the type of leadership style used in University Colleges, 91.2% of respondents indicated strong agreement to the leadership style used in University College as effective compared to only 8.8% who disagreed with the predominant leadership style exhibited by the university leadership. Nasereddin and Sharabati (2016) assert in agreement to the findings that because leadership style depends on the leader, the context and the followers as well as culture, it is important for organisations to go by best fit principle. However, they recommend shared leadership, transformational and transactional leadership for academicians and this strongly supports the findings of this study.

The finding is in consonance with the findings of Samad (2012) that transformational leadership is related to organisational performance therefore perceived to be used much in most organisations. He finds in his study in Malaysian logistics companies that transformational leadership has significant influence on organisational effectiveness and performance. In the same direction, Mutar (2015) in a study finds that transformational leadership positively influences organisational performance and therefore it is important for leaders to harness the characteristics of transformational leadership style in their daily line of duties if they are to achieve effectiveness.

A lot of studies (Howell and Morris, 2009; Johnson, 2009; James, 2005; Scott & Peter, 2009 and Robbinson 2009) affirm the significance of transformational leaderships style to organisations hence its prominence in most institutions. However, from the Table, authoritarian leadership and transactional leadership are perceived to be moderately used in University Colleges.

Summary and Conclusions:

Transformational leadership style emerged as the dominant style used in Private University College by its leadership though transactional, authoritative and laissez faire leadership styles complemented the transformational leadership. 91.2% of respondents indicated strong agreement to the effectiveness of the use of transformational leadership style by the University College leadership however authoritative leadership style contributed more variations in organisational effectiveness in the operations of the university than transactional and laissez faire styles. The findings of the study indicated that Private University leadership exhibited transformational leadership style with transactional, authoritative and laissez faire styles being complementary. The findings agree with full range leadership model which asserts that laissez faire, transactional and transformational leadership styles go through medium level to strong level of efficiency and high engagements to promote organisational effectiveness. It is the variations in the use of leadership styles that enhance situational context of effectiveness of the University community. If university leadership has the competency of

using hybrid of leadership style components, they will be able to propel effectiveness. Transformational leadership and individual level performance are positively correlated as transactional leadership style has a positive association with organisational effectiveness. Authoritarian style used ensures strong control over subordinate's thereby demanding unique obedience from them for which followers focus on the job responsibility with uncertainty leading to organisational effectiveness and productivity within the private universities.

References:

1. Harris, A. et al., (2007). Distributed leadership and organisational change: Reviewing the evidence. *Journal of Educational Change*, 8(4), pp. 337-347.
2. Mitonga-Monga, J. & Coetzee, M., (2012). Perceived leadership style and employee participation. *African Journal of Business Management*, 6(15)
3. Janse, B. (2019). Participative Leadership. tools hero: <https://www.toolshero.com/leadership/participative-leadership-style/> (Accessed on April 17, 2020)
4. Kendra, C. (2020). How a Transactional leadership style works. *Personality psychology very mind*
5. Weber, M. (1947). *The theory of social and economic organisation*. (T.Parsons, Trans.). New York: Free Press.
6. Bryman, A. (1992). *Charisma and leadership in organisations*. London: Sage
7. Bass, B. M. (1985). *Leadership and Performance beyond Expectations*. New York: The Free Press.
8. Whitehead, J. (2018). Directing, coaching, supporting and Delegating are what? <http://johnwhite.com/situational-leadership>
9. Oxford & Burry-Stock (1995). Assessing the use of language learning strategies worldwide with the ESL/EFL version of the Strategy Inventory for Language Learning. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science (JHSS)* ISSN: 2279-0837, ISBN: 2279-0845. Volume 4, Issue 4 (Nov. - Dec. 2012), PP 01-05
10. Wang, G., Oh, I.-S. & Courtright, S. H., (2011). Transformational leadership and performance across criteria and levels: A Meta-Analytic Review of 25 years of research. *Group & Organisation Management*, 36(2), pp. 223-270.
11. Sofi, M. A. & Devanadhen, D. K., (2015). Impact of Leadership Styles on Organisational Performance: An Empirical Assessment of Banking Sector in Jammu and Kashmir. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, 17(8), pp. 31-45.
12. Nasereddin Y.A & Sharabati, A.A. (2016) University leadership style in the light of governance principles. *International review of management and business research* Vol.3
13. Samad, S (2012). The Influence of Innovation and Transformational Leadership on Organisational Performance, *Procedia - Social and Behavioural Sciences*, Volume 57,
14. Howell, T.and Morris (2009). Superiors' Evaluations and Subordinates' Perceptions of Transformational and Transactional Leadership. <http://www.ijrcm.org/articles/cm3.ht>
15. Johnson S. (2019). What is the meaning of organisational Strategy? *Business Planning and Strategy*. CHRON
16. James, k. M. (2005). A Meta-Analysis of Transformational and Transactional Leadership Correlates of Effectiveness and Satisfaction. <http://www.ijrcm.org/articles/cm3.ht>.
17. Scott, M. H and Peter, W.(2009). Empirical Investigation of the Effects of Transformational and Transactional Leadership on Organisational Climate. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 4, 16-18.
18. Robbinson, L. P. (2009). The Implications of Transactional and Transformational Leadership for Individual, team, and Organisational Development. <http://www.ijrcm.org/articles/cm3.ht>. Accessed 26 June 2012.